

Determination of the compositions and accurate thermodynamic association constants of charge-transfer or EDA complexes of TNT and amines using HPTLC with scanning video densitometer

S. P. Sharma^a and S. C. Lahiri*

Central Forensic Science Laboratory, 30, Gorachand Road, Kolkata-700 014, India

E-mail : sprasadsharma@rediffmail.com, sujitclahiri@yahoo.com

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Abstract : TLC and HPTLC had been adjudged as useful tools for the separation, identification and quantification of the drugs, hydrocarbons, alkaloids and explosives. However, HPTLC with scanning video densitometer, though not utilized till now, can be utilized as an ideal tool for determining the compositions and accurate thermodynamic association constants of the organic CT complexes when the donors and acceptors are in equimolar or in almost equimolar ratios, a necessary condition for the determination of accurate K_{DA} values. This is exemplified from the study of the EDA complexes between TNT and amines like isopropylamine, ethylenediamine, bis(3-aminopropyl)amine and tetraethylenepentamine in DMSO. The results are verified and validated from the most extensively used spectrophotometric measurements. In spite of the wide divergence in the methodologies, the results from two different methods agree well.

The method is accurate and can be utilized to determine the stability of any type of complexes. This is an eco-friendly and rapid analytical technique where the requirements of analytes and eluting solvents are small.

Keywords : Amines, association constants, CT or EDA complexes, HPTLC, Kubelka-Munk function, reflectance measurements, TNT, DMSO.

Introduction

Charge-transfer or molecular interactions between electron donors (D) and acceptors (A) are of great importance in view of their varied applications in diverse fields like (a) CT complexes as intermediates in catalytic reactions¹⁻⁴, (b) separation, identification and quantification of organic compounds like alkaloids, drugs, explosives, hydrocarbons⁴⁻¹¹, (c) semiconductivity fields¹²⁻¹⁶ and (d) in understanding the role of weak interactions in drug-receptor interactions and in many biological processes¹⁷⁻²⁵. A number of methods like UV-Visible spectrophotometry, IR and NMR measurements, polarography, calorimetry, dielectric constant measurements have been utilized to determine the positions of the equilibrium and the association constants K_{DA} of donor-acceptor or EDA complexes^{8,17,25,26}. However, spectrophotometric method is the most favored and extensively used method.

Most of the explosives particularly high explosives

are nitro compounds like s-TNB (trinitrobenzene), TNT (trinitrotoluene), tetryl¹ etc. TLC and high performance thin layer chromatography (HPTLC) with the use of suitable chromogenic agents²⁷⁻²⁹, have been found to be valuable tool for the detection, identification and particularly estimation of compounds of medicinal, forensic and environmental interest in traces²⁷. Naturally HPTLC with scanning video-densitometry appears to be a suitable method for the determination of the compositions and association constants of the CT complexes taking D and A in stoichiometric ratios, a necessary condition for the accurate determination of thermodynamic association constants of the CT complexes. But the method, however, has not been properly utilized or taken into consideration. Recently Kuila and Lahiri³⁰ utilized the HPTLC technique for the determination of composition and association constant of the charge transfer complexes keeping D and A in stoichiometric ratios.

^aPresent address : Geological Survey of India, ER, DK-6, Sector-II, Salt Lake City, Kolkata-700 091, India.

The present communication describes the use of HPTLC with video-densitometry for the identification, determination of the compositions and association constants of the complexes between TNT and amines like isopropylamine, ethylenediamine, bis(3-aminopropyl) amine and tetraethylenepentamine in DMSO. It is to be noted that the chromogenic agent 3,3'-iminobispropylamine was used as TLC reagent for identification of a large number of nitroexplosives and nitromusks^{1,28,29}. The nitro compounds and amines were assumed to form CT complexes though the nature of the complexes and their physico-chemical properties were not investigated. The results from the present experiment were verified and validated by most widely used spectrophotometric method. The results of our investigation are presented in this article.

Experimental

TNT (reference standard obtained from High Energy Material Research Laboratory, Pune, India) was used as such. Isopropyl amine, ethylenediamine, bis(3-aminopropyl)amine, tetraethylenepentamine (GR, Fluka, Switzerland) were also used as such. DMSO and other solvents were of HPLC grade (Spectrochem India Pvt. Ltd.).

TNT formed deep red colored complexes with the amines mentioned before. Initial complex formation required several minutes and association constants K_{DA} were measured after 1 h but for ethylenediamine complexes, measurements were made after 24 h.

Determination of the compositions and association constants of the TNT + amine complexes :

E. Merck's precoated TLC plates of 20 cm × 20 cm × 0.25 cm dimensions with silica gel of 80–100 mesh size were used. Equimolar solutions of donors (D) (amines) and TNT (acceptor A) (concentration $1.017 \times 10^{-3} M$) as required to determine the composition of the complex following Job's method of continuous variation were prepared. TNT and amine were mixed in different ratios and the corresponding blank solutions containing TNT were also prepared.

Both the standard (TNT) and experimental (TNT + amine) solutions were spotted by the auto-sampler at different positions on the same plate keeping a 15 mm margin at the bottom and 20 mm each at the right and left sides. Separate but same plate was used for spotting standard reference solutions of TNT and experimental solu-

tion (TNT and amine) for the study of each complex. Each spot was given 5 μL solution. The plates were developed separately in a Camag developing chamber saturated with benzene solvent system and DMSO solvent system. The complex did not move in benzene but move in DMSO. TNT in standard blank solution and unreacted TNT in the complex solutions showed movements in benzene solution. The video-photographs conclusively proved the formation of the complexes (Fig. 1). The developed plates were scanned and the spot areas were measured with a densitometer using a 254 nm light beam, 8 mm length and 1 mm width. Adjustments of length and width were made depending on the sample used to cover fully the spot areas during the scanning of the spots.

Fig. 1. The separation of unreacted TNT and the complex (upper spots are TNT and lower spots are complex).

The differences of the areas of TNT in standard solutions and the corresponding areas of the unreacted TNT in the mixtures were determined. The results are presented in Table 1.

The principle of densitometry and HPTLC measurements for the determination of x , the concentration of complexes in equilibrium solutions is enumerated briefly :

HPTLC experiments are based on the absorptions of the reactants TNT (A) and amines (D) and complexes (DA) on HPTLC plates (fluorescent silica gel of 80–100 mesh) and elution by suitable solvents for the separation of the components and complexes. In HPTLC, detection and quantification of the components were done from *in situ* measurements of the spot areas in the chromatogram in terms of response peak areas versus amount spotted from the diffuse reflectance measurements using 254 nm UV-light. HPTLC measurements at 298 K were made using Desaga, HPTLC system, with auto sampler (model AS30) and scanning was performed with CD 60 densitometer. Video image was captured with Desaga Video documentation system, VD-40.

Table 1. Comparison of *K* of the CT complex of TNT and amines measured by different methods

TNT + Isopropylamine	<i>K</i> value by spectrometrically at 528 nm	2.52×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by iteration at 528 nm	2.94×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by HPTLC method at 528 nm	2.36×10^4
TNT + Ethylenediamine	<i>K</i> value by spectrometrically at 528 nm	8.52×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by iteration at 528 nm	8.98×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by HPTLC at 528 nm	5.40×10^3
TNT + Bis(3-aminopropyl)amine	<i>K</i> value by spectrometrically at 528 nm	1.35×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by iteration at 528 nm	1.16×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by HPTLC at 528 nm	1.32×10^4
TNT + Tetraethylenepentamine	<i>K</i> value by spectrometrically at 528 nm	1.53×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by iteration at 528 nm	1.76×10^4
	<i>K</i> value by HPTLC at 528 nm	1.16×10^4

Densitometry is a suitable tool for qualitative and quantitative estimation of organic substances (drugs, explosives etc.). It is actually scanning of analog curves of the chromatogram tracks arising from the separation of compounds on the TLC plate.

Densitometry measures the intensity or optical density of spots on the same TLC plate from which unknown concentration of a compound is compared to that of known concentration of the same compound. However, the instrument must be calibrated before actual measurement. Calibration is made by spotting a number of standard solutions of TNT on the TLC plate and measuring the reflectance or the optical densities of spots on the chromatographic plates (representing the area of the spots). Desaga HPTLC system with CD 60 densitometer was previously calibrated and used for the estimations of TNT, tetryl and RDX in our laboratory²⁷.

However, the readings of the spots of the calibration curves are likely to be different for different plates but calibrated results for the concentrations of known and unknown solutions will be same for all the plates.

Results and discussion

The association constant of the 1 : 1 complex

can be written as

$$K_{DA} = \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \times \frac{\gamma_{DA}}{\gamma_D \gamma_A} \approx \frac{[DA]}{[D][A]} \quad (2)$$

$$= \frac{x}{(c_z - x)(c_z - x)}$$

γ_{DA} , γ_D and γ_A , the activity coefficients of the uncharged species in solution, were assumed to be unity in the concentration range studied.

Densitometry^{31,32} :

Theory :

Light striking the spot on the opaque plate surface will undergo absorption, scattering, transmission or reflectance. Light transmitted or reflected will be diminished in intensity at these wavelengths forming the absorption profile of the spot. HPTLC plates scatter light strongly and since the pathlength of the light through the sample is unknown, absorption measurements do not obey Beer-Lambert law but Kubelka-Munk³⁴ equation,

$$f(R) = \frac{(1-R)^2}{2R} = \frac{c}{a} = \frac{2.303\epsilon}{s} \left(a = \frac{s}{2.303\epsilon} \right) \quad (3)$$

is utilized for quantification purposes when diffuse reflectance measurements are used.

Here, *R* = diffuse reflectance, *s* = sample dispersion or scatter co-efficient, *c* = spot concentration, ϵ = absorption co-efficient.

Thus, a linear relationship between

$$[f(R)] = mx \quad (4)$$

and concentration of the analyte is expected at low concentrations, passing through the origin but becomes non-linear at higher concentration regions and follows the relation :

$$f(R) = y = mx + c \quad (5)$$

In our experiment, the concentration ranges of TNT used were high and the nonlinear equation had to be utilized

for determining unknown concentrations. However, to avoid any error creeping into the results, the measured areas of the spots (A_1, A_2, A_3 etc.) from unreacted donor (TNT) in the (D+A) mixtures in DMSO were compared with the measured areas (A'_1, A'_2, A'_3 etc.) of spots of TNT in the corresponding blank solutions containing the same concentrations of TNT in DMSO.

Thus, for any compound, $f(R)$ will vary depending on the concentration of the substance on the spot.

The quantitative estimations of the unreacted TNT in experimental solutions (spot areas A_1, A_2, A_3 etc.) and TNT in the corresponding blank solutions (spot areas A'_1, A'_2, A'_3 etc.) were done from *in situ* measurements of the areas of spots in the chromatogram from which unreacted TNT in the solution mixtures were determined using the relation (6).

Concentration of unreacted TNT in

$$I = \frac{\text{Area of spot } A_1}{\text{Area of spot } A_7} \times \text{conc. of TNT in the blank solution} \quad (6)$$

The equilibrium concentrations of TNT and x in solutions can thus be determined directly and individually for each set of solutions.

From the values of x (Table 1) thus determined, the composition of the complexes were found to be 1 : 1 using Job's method of continuous variations. Fig. 2 represents a typical Job's curve. The association constants K_{DA} of the complexes calculated using eq. (2) are presented in Table 1. The beauty of the method lies in the fact that the composition of the complexes can be deter-

Fig. 2. Curve of the Job's method of continuous variations.

mined easily and it is possible to determine the concentration x of the complex for each individual equilibrium solutions prepared for the measurement of K_{DA} .

Measurements were made on the absorption mode and the detection limits were in low nano gram range. No significant error occurred due to the reasons given below :

- (i) The experiments are repetitive and reproducible.
- (ii) The sample matrix did not absorb and the concentration variations were small for any particular solution pair (the experimental solution and the corresponding blank solution).
- (iii) The information depths or optical path lengths for the reflectance measurements were not known but likely to be variable depending on sample type and wavelengths used for measurements. However, in the present experiment, the concentration differences of TNT in solution mixtures and the corresponding blanks were negligible. The scattering properties and the geometry of the reactant (TNT) could be regarded to be the same i.e. optical path length for the measured solution pair may be considered to be same.
- (iv) Spotting errors were eliminated using automated spotting technique.
- (v) Efforts were made to keep R_f values within 0.3–0.7 to ensure equitable distribution of solute in the zone of chromatogram to which it had travelled.
- (vi) HPTLC with scanning video-densitometry is a rapid and accurate method for *in situ* detection and quantification of the spot site, location, interest of separation.

Thus, the results showed that the K_{DA} values can be regarded to be accurate and satisfactory. The complexes are stable and the stability constants of the complexes are almost the same and slight variations may be due to steric factors. The order of stability of the TNT complexes is EDA complex > isopropylamine complex > tetraethylenepentamine complex > bis(3-aminopropyl) complex. The compositions and the association constants determined using HPTLC with scanning densitometry needed verification and validation for which comparison of the results had been made with the results obtained spectrophoto-

metrically, the method most widely used and acclaimed universally.

TNT formed beautifully colored CT complexes with amines and the complexes showed three fairly strong absorption peaks near 370 nm, 528 nm and 629 nm respectively.

The compositions of the complexes were found 1 : 1 in all cases. The spectrophotometric association constant K_{DA} values (with D and A in stoichiometric ratios) agreed well with those obtained using HPTLC method in spite of wide diversity in methodologies used in determining K_{DA} of complexes as given in Table 1.

Table 2. Comparison of the theoretical energy values $[(hv_{CT})_{theo}]$ of the CT complexes utilizing DFT calculations with their corresponding experimental energy values $[(hv_{CT})_{exp}]$

Name of compound	Level of theory	Basis set	$[(hv_{CT})_{theo}]$ (eV)	Abs. peak (nm)	$[(hv_{CT})_{exp}]$ (eV)	Abs. peak (nm)	$[(hv_{CT})_{exp}]$ (eV)	Abs. peak (nm)	$[(hv_{CT})_{exp}]$ (eV)
IPA + TNT	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	3.617	528	2.350	–	–	378	3.282
EDA + TNT	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	3.353	530	2.341	463	2.680	378	3.282
BAPA + TNT	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.850	532	2.332	462	2.686	366	3.390
TEPA + TNT	TD-B3LYP	6-311G (d,p)	2.977	530	2.341	468	2.651	368	3.372

Table 3A. Comparison of electron affinity values of TNT and ionization potential values of different donors using differences in energy value of TNT and the corresponding anion $[E_A^{Ad}]$ and that of different cations $[I_D^{Ad}]$; and using Mulliken's theorem $[E_A^V$ and $I_D^V]$; and Koopman's theorem $[E_A^V(Koop)$ and $I_D^V(Koop)]$ considering both the complete transfer of electron ($G_1 = 4.13$) and the partial transfer of electrons (G_1') which are different for different donors for peak 1

Donor of the complex (nm)	λ_{max} of the complex (nm)	Ionization potential of donors (eV)			Electron affinity of TNT (eV)								
		I_D^{Ad}	I_D^V	I_D^V (Koop)	Theoretical			Calculated from the experimental data					
					E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	(considering $G_1 = 4.13$)			(considering partial charge-transfer G_1')		
IPA	528	9.252	7.212	6.322	0.843	–	2.704	2.940	1.633	0.625	–13.329	–14.630	–15.644
EDA	530	8.708	7.092	6.058		5.345					–14.240	–15.542	–16.556
BAPA	532	7.619	6.614	5.555							–15.643	–16.944	–17.958
TEPA	530	7.347	6.613	5.681							–16.484	–17.786	–18.799

Table 3B. Comparison of electron affinity values of TNT and ionization potential values of different donors using differences in energy value of TNT and the corresponding anion $[E_A^{Ad}]$ and that of different cations $[I_D^{Ad}]$; and using Mulliken's theorem $[E_A^V$ and $I_D^V]$; and Koopman's theorem $[E_A^V(Koop)$ and $I_D^V(Koop)]$ considering both the complete transfer of electron ($G_1 = 4.13$) and the partial transfer of electrons (G_1') which are different for different donors for peak 2

Donor of the complex (nm)	λ_{max} of the complex (nm)	Ionization potential of donors (eV)			Electron affinity of TNT (eV)								
		I_D^{Ad}	I_D^V	I_D^V (Koop)	Theoretical			Calculated from the experimental data					
					E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	(considering $G_1 = 4.13$)			(considering partial charge-transfer G_1')		
IPA	–	9.252	7.212	6.322	0.843	–	2.704	2.510	1.431	0.345	–	–	–
EDA	463	8.708	7.092	6.058		5.345					–14.671	–15.750	–16.836
BAPA	462	7.619	6.614	5.555							–16.073	–17.152	–18.238
TEPA	468	7.347	6.613	5.681							–16.914	–17.993	–19.079

Table 3C. Comparison of electron affinity values of TNT and ionization potential values of different donors using differences in energy value of TNT and the corresponding anion [E_A^{Ad}] and that of different cations [I_D^{Ad}]; and using Mulliken's theorem [E_A^V and I_D^V]; and Koopman's theorem [$E_A^V(Koop)$ and $I_D^V(Koop)$] considering both the complete transfer of electron ($G_1 = 4.13$) and the partial transfer of electrons (G_1') which are different for different donors for peak 3

Donor complex	λ_{max} (nm)	Ionization potential of donors (eV)			Electron affinity of TNT (eV)								
		I_D^{Ad}	I_D^V	I_D^V (Koop)	Theoretical			Calculated from the experimental data					
					E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)	E_A^{Ad}	E_A^V	E_A^V (Koop)
								(considering $G_1 = 4.13$)			(considering partial charge-transfer G_1')		
IPA	378	9.252	7.212	6.322	0.843	-	2.704	2.952	0.826	0.258	-13.316	-15.442	-16.011
EDA	378	8.708	7.092	6.058		5.345					-14.228	-16.354	-16.923
BAPA	366	7.619	6.614	5.555							-15.630	-17.757	-18.325
TEPA	368	7.347	6.613	5.681							-16.471	-18.598	-19.166

However, there is one important lacuna of HPTLC method i.e. the energies due to charge transfer complex formation cannot be determined. But it is possible to make theoretical calculations quantum mechanically using density function theory (DFT) to find out CT energies of the complexes and compare the CT energy values using the spectrophotometric absorption maximum values described before. Vertical ionization potentials of donors I_D^V and electronegativity E_A^V of TNT (acceptor) and experimental (calculated from spectrophotometric absorption data) and theoretical (calculated using DFT³⁵) charge transfer energy values are given in Tables 2 and 3.

However, in spectrophotometry, the compositions of the complexes cannot be determined in many cases and the association constants K_{DA} values are usually determined using Benesi-Hilderbrand equation³⁶ with $D \gg A$ which gives variable association constant values depending on the conditions and concentrations of D and A. But the condition $D \gg A$ or $A \gg D$ forces the equilibrium for reaction (1) to the right and thermodynamic reversibility is lost and K_{DA} values determined under the condition cannot be accurate thermodynamic K_{DA} values^{24,30}.

Moreover, there is always uncertainty in determining $1/\epsilon$ values from the intercepts which means uncertainty in spectrophotometrically determined K_{DA} values also. But HPTLC with densitometry, uncertainly may be due to reflectance measurements of the area of the spots of solutions containing unknown concentration of the donor (D) at equilibrium vis-à-vis the known concentration of donor

in the respective standard solution for any particular pair. Naturally the error will be reasonably small and the equilibrium concentration of x of any individual solution can be determined directly.

HPTLC with video-densitometry can thus be regarded to be a reliable method for the determination of the association constants K_{DA} of CT complexes or any other complexes in non-aqueous solvents.

Conclusion

- (i) HPTLC is a suitable method for detection and also quantification of the CT complex which can be video documented.
- (ii) HPTLC can be used as a valuable tool for the accurate determination of the composition and the association constants K_{DA} of the CT complexes and equilibrium constants of other complexes as well with suitable eluting solvents.
- (iii) A single plate can be utilized for a number of reference and standard samples side by side and it is a rapid method of determination of K_{DA} .
- (iv) The sample and solvent (including the solvent in the mobile phase) requirements are very small.
- (v) The method is cost effective and eco-friendly and lies in the domain of green chemistry.

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